

Antimicrobial Efficacy of Some Medicinal Plants on Different Bacterial Isolates Associated with Semen of Infertile Men

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Infection of the male genitourinary tract represents a significant health care problem and account for almost 15% of cases of male infertility. The present study aims to isolate and identified different bacterial isolates collected from semen samples of infertile men attending to infertility clinic and evaluation of the effects of bacteriospermia on semen quality. Five medicinal plants extracts were used as an alternative therapeutic agent targeting these isolates. Seventy seven infertile men were evaluated by standard bacterial culture methods. Among total cases, 22 cases (28.6%) showed at least one pathogen: 10 (45.5%) *Escherichia coli*, 9 (40.9%) *Staphylococcus aureus*, and 3 (13.6%) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Our results showed that samples infected with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* recorded the highest ratio of abnormalities (96.5%). On the other hand samples infected with *Escherichia coli* recorded the second highest ratio of abnormalities (93.75%), while the samples

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infected by *Staphylococcus aureus* showed the least ratio of abnormalities (92.88%). From these five medicinal plants that extracted by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods, the most potent plants extracts against bacterial isolates were detected for both *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) and *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme). In conclusion, the present study showed that the microbiological investigation should be performed, as a routine test, to all infertile men attending to infertility clinics. Flavonoids of the selected plants have a good antioxidant and antibacterial activity, and can be used for medicinal and therapeutic applications.

Keywords: Semen; bacterial isolates; men infertility; medicinal plant extracts.

1. INTRODUCTION

Infection is a powerful mechanism that can lead to sperm damage, deformity and eventually, male infertility. Genital tract infection and inflammation have been associated to 8-35% of male infertility cases [1]. Infection can affect different sites of the male reproductive tract, such as the testis, the epididymis and male accessory sex glands [2,3]. Spermatozoa subsequently can be affected by infections at different points in their development and maturation. Acute and chronic infections can compromise spermatogenesis, resulting in quantitative and qualitative reductions [3,4]. Among bacterial species that interact with spermatozoa are well known causative pathogens of genitourinary tract infection such as *Escherichia coli*, *Ureaplasma urealyticum*, *Mycoplasma hominis* and *Chlamydia trachomatis* [5,6,7].

E. coli probably represents the most frequently isolated microorganism in genitourinary infections. *E. coli* rapidly adheres to human spermatozoa *in vitro*, resulting in agglutination of spermatozoa [8]. Agglutination of spermatozoa was produced only by live pathogenic *E. coli* whereas killed bacteria failed to do so [9]. While studying other uropathogenic microorganisms found significant decrease in sperm motility when spermatozoa were co-incubated with *Staphylococcus aureus*. Jiang and Lu [10] reported that *S. aureus* was the predominant flora in infertile men with a significant decrease in sperm motility. *S. aureus* was one of the predominant flora in the infertile men and commonly present in the cervix of females immobilizes the spermatozoa [11]. Attempts to improve the efficacy of available antibiotics, particularly the older and cheaper ones have been suggested [12].

Medicinal plants continue to play a central role in the healthcare systems of large proportions of the world's population, particularly in developing countries, where herbal medicine has a long and

uninterrupted history of use [13]. This raises the prospects of obtaining novel chemotherapeutic compounds if this vastly untapped resource could be adequately explored. The prospect of obtaining drugs from plants has been demonstrated by some notable examples of important pharmaceuticals derived from plant precursors [14]. The rich chemical diversity in plants has also been reported to be a promising source of antibacterial compounds raising hopes of obtaining novel antibiotics that can aid the fight against resistant infection [15].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection of Samples

Seminal fluid specimens were collected from males attending the fertility clinic at the International Islamic Center for Population Studies and Research (IICPSR), Al-Azhar University, Cairo, Egypt. The samples were collected from patients during the period of April 2013 to December 2014. Upon collection, samples were transferred to the laboratory in a temperature that is as close as possible to body by placing the container inside a plastic bag.

2.2 Examination of Specimens

All semen samples included in this study were examined for physical appearance, volume, viscosity, total motility, and sperm count.

2.2.1 Appearance

Semen samples were examined immediately after liquefaction or within one hour of ejaculation. A normal sample has homogenous gray opalescent appearance. It may appear less opaque if the sperm concentration is very low or brown when red blood cells are present.

2.2.2 Volume

The volume of the seminal fluid was measured by decanting the whole sample aseptically into a

graduated centrifuge tube and the level was recorded in ml \pm 0.1. The universal bottle was preserved for cultural examination and for further experimentation.

2.2.3 Viscosity

The viscosity of the sample was determined with the aid of Pasteur pipette. A drop of semen was allowed to fall back to the sample and the length of the thread was observed. A normal sample leaves the pipette as small discrete drops while in abnormal cases, the drop forms a thread greater than 2 cm long.

2.2.4 Total motility

Total motility of the samples was done by applying a drop of the sample onto a slide, covered with cover slip. The sample was then viewed under the microscope using x40 objective lens. The microscopic field was scanned systemically and the motility of each spermatozoon encountered was graded a, b, c and d that is, (a) Rapid progressive motility, (b) Slow or sluggish motility, (c) Nonprogressive motility and (d) Immobility. The number of spermatozoa in each category was counted with the aid of a laboratory counter. Usually, four to six fields were scanned to classify 100 successive spermatozoa. All motile spermatozoa with the ones that had their heads moving were recorded.

2.2.5 Sperm count

Improved Neubauer Counting Chamber was used for the count. One twenty (1/20) dilution of semen was done with formol saline as diluents. Count = $N \times 10^6$ /ml.

2.3 Cultural Methods

Culture of seminal fluid samples were cultured in aseptic condition, within 1 h of collection the seminal fluids were cultured

using Blood Agar, Chocolate Agar and MacConkey Agar media and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The cultures were examined for bacterial growth; the isolation and identification of bacterial isolates were carried out according to Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology. All our identified strains were confirmed by 16s ribosomal RNA.

2.4 Plant Extractions

Two different methods were used for extracting the active components from the five medicinal plants used (Table 1). The source of the five medicinal plants was provided kindly by faculty of agriculture, Cairo University. Accepted names of plant species were listed according to the following link: www.theplantlist.org database.

2.4.1 Extraction methods

Two different extraction methods were used for extracting the active components from the medicinal plants as the following:

2.4.1.1 Ethanol-methanol

Fifty grams of crushed plant material was packed in percolator and extracted with 100 ml of 95% ethanol [16].

2.4.1.2 Chloroform-methanol

Fifty grams of crushed plant material was homogenized with chloroform /methanol (2/1) to a final volume 100 ml [17].

2.5 Screening for the Antimicrobial Potential of the Medicinal Plant Extracts

A concentration of 0.5 McFarland standards was prepared from fresh cultures of microorganisms.

Table 1. Five medicinal plants were used in the present study

Code	Common name	Scientific Name	Family	Part used
Z	Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	Rhizome
A	Chamomile	<i>Chamaemelum nobile</i> (L.) All	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Flower
T	Thyme	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L.	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Flower
S	Clove	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr. & L. M. Perry	<i>Myrtaceae</i>	Buds
R	Rosemary	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Leaves

Each microorganism was inoculated on the surface of Mueller-Hinton agar plates. Subsequently, filter paper discs (6 mm in diameter) saturated with each extract (50 µL) was placed on surface of each inoculated plate [18].

2.6 Screening for the Antimicrobial Potential of the Plant Extract Fractions

A concentration of 0.5 McFarland standards was prepared from fresh cultures of microorganisms. Each microorganism was inoculated on the surface of Mueller-Hinton agar plates. Subsequently, filter paper discs (6 mm in diameter) saturated with plant extract fractions (50 µL) were placed on surface of each inoculated plate [18]. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. After this period, it was possible to observe inhibition zone. Cultured bacteria with halos equal to or greater than 7 mm were considered susceptible to the tested extract. The control was the solvent used.

2.7 Thin Layer Chromatography

Thin layer chromatography technique (TLC) was used for testing purity of the more potent antibacterial fraction of the plant extract [19,20].

2.8 Identification of Pure Antibacterial Compound

Purified antibacterial compounds were identified by physical and spectral measurements using Ultraviolet Spectroscopic Analysis, ¹H-NMR spectroscopy, and ¹³C-NMR Spectroscopy [21,22,23].

3. RESULTS

3.1 Frequency of Bacterial Isolates

Seventy seven samples of semen collected from men attending the fertility clinic of the International Islamic Center for Population Studies and Research (IICPSR), were examined routinely, for normal semen characteristics and bacterial count. Among total cases, 22 cases (28.6%) showed at least one pathogen. Three genera of bacterial isolates were obtained and these include *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with the highest counts recorded for the genera

Escherichia coli 10 (45.5%), *Staphylococcus aureus* 9 (40.9%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 3 (13.6%) (Table 2).

3.2 Distribution of Isolates Relative to Sperm Characteristics

Tables 2 showed the distribution of the bacterial isolates relative to sperm characteristics including sperm count, total motility, progressive motility and abnormalities. In the present study the semen samples infected by *Staphylococcus aureus* showed higher sperm count (4.62×10^6) than *Escherichia coli* (4.53×10^6) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (4.03×10^6) that showed lowest sperm count.

The highest total and progressive motility were recorded from samples infected with *Staphylococcus aureus*, the motility was 25% and 8.33%, respectively. Regarding to samples infected with *Escherichia coli*, the total and progressive motility was 15.1% and 6.5% respectively. The least motility parameters were recorded with samples infected with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, the total and progressive motility was 1.67% and 0.00% respectively.

The results showed that samples infected with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* recorded the highest ratio of abnormalities (96.5%). On the other hand samples infected with *Escherichia coli* recorded the second highest ratio of abnormalities (93.75%), while the samples infected by *Staphylococcus aureus* showed the least ratio of abnormalities (92.88%) (Table 3).

3.3 Identification of Bacterial Strains by Biochemical and 16s Ribosomal RNA

The bacterial strains identification was carried out according to Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology (Buchanan, Gibbons, 1978; Gerhardt et al. 1994). All our identified strains were confirmed by 16s ribosomal RNA. Sequences were compared with bacterial strains sequences in the GenBank database using BLASTN (Table 4).

3.4 Antimicrobial Activity Caused by Different Medicinal Plant Extracts

The antimicrobial activities of five medicinal plants against our bacterial isolates were

Table 2. Frequencies of bacterial isolates in the present study

Group	Bacterial isolate	Frequency	Percentage (%)
A	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	10	45.5
B	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	9	40.9
C	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	3	13.6

Table 3. The distribution of isolates relative to sperm characteristics

Group	Bacterial isolates	Percentage (%)	Sperm count	Total motility (%)	Progressive motility (%)	Abnormalities (%)
A	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	45.5	4.53 x 10 ⁶	15.1	6.5	93.75
B	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	40.9	4.62 x 10 ⁶	25	8.33	92.88
C	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	13.6	4.03 x 10 ⁶	1.67	0.00	96.5

3.3.1 Bacterial samples sequences

3.3.1.1 Samples No. 1: *Escherichia coli*

TTGGCGCTGC GTCAGGCCTA CACATGCAGA GAGGTAACAG GAAGAGCTTG CTTCTTTGCT
 GACGAGTGGC GGACGGGTGA GTAATGTCTG GGAACTGCC TGATGGAGGG GGATAACTAC
 TGGAAACGGT AGCTAATACC GCATAACGTC GCAAGACCAA AGAGGGGGAC CTTCCGGCCT
 CTTGCCATCG GATGTGCCA GATGGGATTA GCTTGTGGT GGGGTAACGG CTCACCAAGG
 CGACGATCCC TAGCTGGTCT GAGAGGATGA CCAGCCACAC TGGAAGTGG ACACGGTCCA
 GACTCCTACG GGAGGCAGCA GTGGGGAATA TTGCACAATG GGCGCAAGCC TGATGCAGCC
 ATGCCGCGTG TATGAAGAAG GCCTTCGGGT TGTAAGTAC TTTCAGCGGG GAGGAAGGGA
 GTAAAGTTAA TACCTTTGCT CATTGACGTT ACCCGCAGAA GAAGCACCGG CTAACTCCGT
 GCCAGCAGCC GCGGTAATAA

3.3.1.2 Samples No. 2: *Staphylococcus aureus*

CGTAGACCGC TGGCCGGCGT GCCTAATACA TGCAAGTCGA GCGAACGGAC GAGAAGCTTG
 CTTCTCTGAT GTTAGCGGCG GACGGGTGAG TAACACGTGG ATAACCTACC TATAAGACTG
 GGATAACTTC GGGAAACCGG AGCTAATACC GGATAATATT TTGAACCGCA TGGTTCAAAA
 GTGAAAGACG GTCTTGCTGT CACTTATAGA TGGATCCGCG CTGCATTAGC TAGTTGGTAA
 GGTAACGGCT TACCAAGGCA ACGATGCATA GCCGACCTGA GAGGGTGATC GGCCACACTG
 GAACTGAGAC ACGGTCCAGA CTCCTACGGG AGGCAGCAGT AGGGAATCTT CCGCAATGGG
 CGAAAGCCTG ACGGAGCAAC GCCGCGTGAG TGATGAAGGT CTTCCGATCG TAAACTCTG
 TTATTAGGGA AGAACATATG TGTAAGTAAC TGTGCACATC TTGACGGTAC CTAATCAGAA
 AGCCACGGCT
 AACTACGTGC CAGCAGCCGC GGTAATAA

3.3.1.3 Samples No. 3: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

TGCGCTGCGG CAGGCCTAAC ACATGCAAGT CGAGCGGATG AAGGGAGCTT GCTCCTGGAT
 TCAGCGGCGG ACGGGTGAGT AATGCCTAGG AATCTGCCTG GTAGTGGGGG ATAACGTCCG
 GAAACGGGCG CTAATACCGC ATACGTCCTG AGGGAGAAAAG TGGGGGATCT TCGGACCTCA
 CGCTATCAGA TGAGCCTAGG TCGGATTAGC TAGTTGGTGG GTTAAAGGCC TACCAAGGCG
 ACGATCCGTA ACTGGTCTGA GAGGATGATC AGTCACACTG GAACTGAGAC ACGGTCCAGA
 CTCCTACGGG AGGCAGCAGT GGGGAATATT GGACAATGGG CGAAAGCCTG ATCCAGCCAT
 GCCGCGTGTG TGAAGAAGGT CTTCCGATTG TAAAGCACTT TAAGTTGGGA GGAAGGGCAG
 TAAGTTAATA CCTTGCTGTT TTGACGTTAC CAACAGAATA AGCACCGGCT AACTTCGTGC
 CAGCAGCCGC GCCAAATAA

Table 4. 16s RNA for bacterial isolates included in our study. Our result showed the bacterial strains were *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Sequences were compared with sequences in the GenBank database using BLASTN

Samples cod#	Hologogue sequences (Sequences identity %)	Accession number
S#1	• <i>Escherichia coli</i> str. K-12 substr. MG1655, complete genome (98%)	NC 000913.3
	• <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157:H7 str. Sakai chromosome, complete genome (98%)	NC 002695.1
	• <i>Escherichia coli</i> O83:H1 str. NRG 857C chromosome, complete genome (97%)	NC 017634.1
S#2	• <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> subsp. aureus NCTC 8325 chromosome, complete genome (99%)	NC 007795.1
	• <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> subsp. aureus N315 chromosome, complete genome (99%)	NC 002745.2
	• <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> ATCC 12228 chromosome, complete genome (97%)	NC 004461.1
S#3	• <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> PAO1 chromosome, complete genome (99%)	NC 002516.2
	• <i>Pseudomonas denitrificans</i> ATCC 13867, complete genome (97%)	NC 020829.1
	• <i>Pseudomonas stutzeri</i> A1501 chromosome, complete genome (97%)	NC 009434.1

present study, two different extraction methods were used for extracting the active components from the medicinal plants as the following:

3.4.1 Ethanol- Methanol extract methods

The results showed that *Escherichia coli* was sensitive for both *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) and *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme), while *Staphylococcus aureus* was sensitive to all plant extracts included our study by ethanol-methanol methods. Regarding to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* it was sensitive to *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) alone. From these five medicinal plants that extracted by methanol-ethanol method, the most potent plants extracts against bacterial isolates were detected for both

Syzygium aromaticum (Clove) and *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme) (Table 5).

3.4.2 Chloroform – methanol extract method

The results showed that *Escherichia coli* was sensitive for both *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) and *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme), while *Staphylococcus aureus* was sensitive to all plant extracts except *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger). Regarding to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* it was sensitive to *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) alone. From these five medical plants that extracted by chloroform-methanol method, the most potent plants extracts against bacterial isolates were detected for both *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) and *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme) (Table 6).

Table 5. Antimicrobial activity for medicinal plants extracted by ethanol-methanol methods against selected bacterial isolates (inhibition zone/mm)

Isolates/Medicinal plant	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	-	16	-
<i>Chamaemelum nobile</i> (L.) All	-	18	-
<i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L.	8	19	-
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr. & L. M. Perry	12	23	10
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.	-	13	-
Control	-	-	-

Table 6. Antimicrobial activity for medicinal plants extracted by chloroform-methanol methods against selected bacterial isolates (inhibition zone/mm)

Isolates/medicinal plant	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	-	-	-
<i>Chamaemelum nobile</i> (L.) All	-	15	-
<i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L.	8	19	-
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr. & L. M. Perry	10	16	9
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.	-	13	-
Control	-	-	-

3.5 Fractionation by Column Chromatography for the Most Potent Medicinal Plant

Syzygium aromaticum was chosen for fractionated after extraction by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods because it has the most potent activity against all bacterial isolates, 15 fractions for each method were collected separately. All fractions were tested for determination the most potent fraction against our bacterial isolates by agar diffusion method.

3.5.1 Antimicrobial activity of *Syzygium aromaticum* fractions after extraction by ethanol-methanol method

Table 7 showed that fraction number 8 was the most potent fraction against all bacterial isolates using agar diffusion method.

3.5.2 Antimicrobial activity of *Syzygium aromaticum* fractions after extraction by chloroform-methanol method

Table 8 showed that fraction number 8 was the most potent fraction against all bacterial isolates using agar diffusion method.

3.6 Photochemical Characterization and Structure Elucidation of the Most Potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum*

For photochemical characterization and structure elucidation of the most potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* physical properties and spectra profile were carried out. Fraction no. 8 for *Syzygium aromaticum* was the most potent fraction has biological activity against all bacterial isolates extracted by both ethanol-methanol and chloroform-methanol methods. The spectroscopic analysis of these active fractions using UV spectrum and NMR spectrum were carried out.

3.6.1 Photochemical characterization and structure elucidation of the most potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* using ethanol-methanol method

Physical properties and spectra profile were assessed for elucidation and identification fraction number 8 that showed the most potent activity against all bacterial isolates using ethanol-methanol method. These physical properties and spectra profile (Table 9), UV spectrum (Fig. 1), ¹HNMR spectrum (Fig. 2) and ¹³CNMR spectrum (Fig. 3) confirmed that this compound was elucidated and identified as Apigenin-7-O- glucoside (C₂₁H₂₁O₁₁).

3.6.2 Photochemical characterization and structure elucidation of the most potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* using chloroform-methanol method

Physical properties and spectra profile were assessed for elucidation and identification fraction number 8 too that showed the most potent activity against all bacterial isolates using chloroform-methanol method. These physical properties and spectra profile (Table 10), UV spectrum (Fig. 4), ¹HNMR spectrum (Fig. 5) and ¹³CNMR spectrum (Fig. 6) confirmed that this compound was elucidated and identified as Apigenin (C₁₅H₁₀O₅).

4. DISCUSSION

Male urogenital tract infection is an important cause of men infertility. The etiological role of infections in male infertility has been paid attention in recent years. Asymptomatic bacteriospermia may play a major role [24,25]. Infectious processes may lead to deterioration of spermatogenesis, impairment of sperm function and obstruction of the seminal tract [26]. As a result, microbiological investigation can reveal a probable infection.

Table 7. Antimicrobial activity of *Syzygium aromaticum* fractions after extraction by ethanol-methanol method (inhibition zone/mm)

Fractions numbers	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
control	-	-	-
Fr.1	16	-	-
Fr.2	10	-	-
Fr.3	8	9	-
Fr.4	10	8	-
Fr.5	-	12	-
Fr.6	8	8	-
Fr.7	11	10	-
Fr.8	20	18	10
Fr.9	16	18	10
Fr.10	14	14	-
Fr.11	8	10	8
Fr.12	-	-	-
Fr.13	-	-	-
Fr.14	-	-	-
Fr.15	-	-	-

Table 8. Antimicrobial activity of *Syzygium aromaticum* fractions after extraction by chloroform-methanol method (inhibition zone /mm)

Fractions numbers	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
control	-	-	-
Fr.1	12	14	-
Fr.2	8	10	-
Fr.3	15	20	-
Fr.4	14	22	8
Fr.5	9	18	-
Fr.6	8	18	-
Fr.7	13	18	8
Fr.8	18	25	9
Fr.9	16	24	9
Fr.10	-	21	-
Fr.11	-	20	-
Fr.12	-	-	-
Fr.13	-	-	-
Fr.14	-	12	-
Fr.15	-	-	-

Table 9. Photochemical characterization and structure elucidation of the most potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* using ethanol-methanol method

Physical and spectra data profile	Structure
<p>R_f: Acetic acid 15%: 0.18, BAW: 0.68, COLOR :U.V.: Violet, U.V. + NH₃: Yellow green, U.V.: MeOH: 227 sh, 273, 335, NaOMe: 275, 306 sh, ▲389, AlCl₃: 277, 330 sh, ▲380, AlCl₃+HCl: 279, 302 sh, ▲383, NaOAc: 280, 340, ▲390, NaOAc+H₃BO₃: 276, 342, ¹H NMR : (DMSO-D₆), δ: 2(s, 4H, alip-OH), 2.5(d, 1H, alip-H), 3.2(m, 4H, alip-H), 4(m, 1H, alip-H), 5(s, 2H, Ar -H), 5.8(s, 1H, Ar-H), 6.3 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2 (m, 5H, J=5.7, Ar-H), ¹³CNMR : (DMSO-D₆), δ: 66(1), 68(1), 70(1), 73(1), 82(1), 96(1), 98(1), 105(2), 116(2), 124(1), 129(1), 155(1), 159(1), 162(1), 166(1), 170(1), 183(1), C₂₁H₂₁O₁₁: Apigenin-7-O- glucoside.</p>	

Fig. 1. UV spectrum of *Syzygium aromaticum* fraction extracted by ethanol–methanol method

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of *Syzygium aromaticum* fraction extracted by ethanol–methanol methods

The present study aims to isolate and identified different bacterial isolates collected from semen of infertile males attending infertility center at International Islamic center for population studies and Research, Al-Azhar University. Five medicinal plants extracts were used as an alternative therapeutic agent targeting these isolates. Fractionation of the most antimicrobial active extracts against the bacterial isolates was done. Phytochemical screening on the most

antimicrobial active fractions and its identification was carried out using spectroscopic analysis. Seventy seven samples of semen were collected and examined for normal semen characteristics and bacterial count. Among total cases, 22 cases (28.6%) showed at least one pathogen. Three genera of bacterial isolates were obtained and these include *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with the highest counts recorded for the genera

Escherichia 10 (45.5%), *Staphylococcus* 9 (40.9%) and *Pseudomonas* 3 (13.6%). Our study was in agreement with previous studies examined the impact of genital tract infections and bacterial semen contamination in male fertility and should that microorganisms can affect the male reproductive function directly, causing the agglutination of motile sperm, reducing the ability of acrosome reaction and causing alterations in cell morphology-and indirectly, through the production of reactive

oxygen species generated by the inflammatory response to the infection [27]. Our study was in agreement with Emokpae et al. [28] reported that presence of *S. aureus* should not be ignored as it can lead to decrease in the number of spermatozoa, the suppression of their motility, changes in their morphology and fertilizing capacity, *S. aureus* could be the dominant flora in infertile men with a significant decrease in sperm motility.

Table 10. Photochemical characterization and structure elucidation of the most potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* using chloroform-methanol method

Physical and spectra data profile	Structure
<p>R_f: Acetic acid 15%: 0.09, BAW: 0.85, COLOR :U.V.: Violet, U.V. + NH₃: Faint Yellow, U.V.: MeOH: 271, 340, NaOMe: ▲ 279, ▲ 400, AlCl₃: 280, 301 sh, 391, AlCl₃+ HCl: 275, ▲ 394, NaOAc: 271, ▼ 382, NaOAc+ H₃BO₃: 270, 342, ¹H NMR (DMSO-D₆), δ: 5(s, 3H, Ar-OH), 6.3(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.1(m, 3H, Ar-OH), 7.8(s, 2H, Ar-H), ¹³C NMR (DMSO-D₆), δ: 97(1), 105(1), 108(1), 116(2), 122(1), 130(1), 156(1), 160(1), 165(1), 168(1), 182(1), C₁₅H₁₀O₅: Apigenin.</p>	

Fig. 3. ¹³C NMR spectrum of *Syzygium aromaticum* fraction extracted by ethanol–methanol methods

Fig. 4. UV spectrum of *Syzygium aromaticum* fraction extracted by chloroform–methanol method

Fig. 5. ¹H NMR spectrum of *Syzygium aromaticum* fraction extracted by chloroform–methanol methods

Bacterial growth may be one cause of contradictory conclusions concerning the effective sperm/bacteria ratio. The absence of sperm agglutination was also observed after heat treatment of bacteria. In one of the earlier reports on effect of heat killed bacteria on spermatozoa characteristics had studied that the live

pathogenic *S. aureus* obtained from cervical cultures decreases in motility and viability of human spermatozoa which was absent in the sets in which the bacteria had been killed by boiling for 30 min before mixing the ejaculate [29].

Fig. 6. ¹³CNMR spectrum of *Syzygium aromaticum* fraction extracted by chloroform–methanol methods

Alternatively, effect of antimicrobial agents on bacteria was also observed. Treatment of cultured bacteria with different groups of antibiotics abolished the effect. This indicates that must be some adhesion sites on spermatozoa to which *E. coli* binds. The mechanisms by which *E. coli* affect sperm functions have not yet been identified [30]. Interference of *E. coli* with these receptors may influence the motility and viability. Other authors reported similar observations concerning sperm motility and agglutination after incubation with *E. coli*. We suggest in agreement with previous study that *E. coli*/spermatozoa-interaction may be a two-step process: i.e. adhesion to and subsequent destruction of the sperm membrane. This mechanism may account for any inhibitory effects of *E. coli* infection on male fertility. It is speculative whether the same mechanisms are also responsible for impaired male fertility in cases of genitourinary infections [30].

According to World Health Organization reported that approximately 75-80% of the world's population uses plant medicines either in part or entirely. Growing numbers of American health care consumers are turning to plant medicines for many reasons – low cost and seeking natural

alternatives with fewer side effects are commonly cited [31].

In the present study five medicinal plants were collected from different locations in Egypt. Each medicinal plant coded and determined its family. Common and scientific name was recorded. Flower of Chamomile and Thyme, Rhizome of Ginger, buds of Clove and leaves of Rosemary were included. These five medicinal plants were extracted by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods and examined as antimicrobial activity against all bacterial isolates included our study.

Our results showed that *Escherichia coli* was sensitive for both *Syzygium aromaticum* and *Thymus vulgaris*, while *Staphylococcus aureus* was sensitive to most plant extracts included our study by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods. Regarding to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* it was sensitive to *Syzygium aromaticum* alone. From these five medicinal plants that extracted by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods, the most potent plants extracts against bacterial isolates were detected for both *Syzygium aromaticum* and *Thymus vulgaris*.

Our results was in agreement with Rasool results revealed that the degree of antimicrobial properties of four spices tested alone against *E. coli* growth can be put in the following order: (clove > rosemary > ginger and cumin), clove and rosemary essential oils alone were exhibited a strong antibacterial action. These spices may be selected as potentially useful anti *E. coli* agents in meat products and other foods which easily contaminated by *E. coli* through fecal oral route during bad handlings, a possible way to use these two spices in combination with other food preservatives such as salt, acid, sugar and others to select pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms and may provide better alternatives in the conventional antimicrobial additives in food [32].

In the present study *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) was chosen for fractionated after extraction by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods because it has the most potent activity against all bacterial isolates, 15 fractions for each method were collected separately. All fractions were tested for determination the most potent fraction against our bacterial isolates by agar diffusion method. According to our data one fraction from each extract has the most potent activity against all bacterial isolates included our study. Photochemical characterization including UV spectrum, NMR spectrum and structure elucidation of the most potent fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* was carried out. This Fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* that extracted by ethanol-methanol and/or chloroform-methanol methods was elucidated and identified as **Apigenin-7-O- glucoside (C₂₁H₂₁O₁₁)** and **Apigenin (C₁₅H₁₀O₅)**, respectively.

Apigenin-7-O- glucoside

Apigenin

Our results was in agreements with Hoque et al. [33] who reported that ethanol and aqueous extracts and the EOs from Clove and cinnamon exhibited antibacterial activity against food borne pathogens *in vitro*. However, there are some limitations in using spices like Clove or cinnamon, such as the antibacterial activity is decreased when spices are added to food materials containing protein, carbohydrate, and fat, and the strong flavor. The flavor of the food products may not be acceptable by some consumer groups if large amounts of spices are added to the products to inhibit the food borne pathogens. Therefore, the use of spices along with preservatives such as acid, salt, sugar and with processing and storage conditions can help in controlling microorganisms in food products.

The spectroscopic analysis currently one of the most versatile and sensitive instrumental methods applied to structural characterization of plant secondary metabolite mixtures isolated from biological material including flavonoid glycoconjugates. Resolution of the applied mass spectrometers plays an important role in structural studies of mixtures of the target compounds isolated from biological material. High-resolution analyzers allow obtaining information about elemental composition of the analyzed compounds. Application of various mass spectrometric techniques, including different systems of ionization, analysis of both positive and negative ions of flavonoids, fragmentation of the protonated/deprotonated molecules and in some cases addition of metal ions to the studied compounds before ionization and fragmentation, may improve structural characterization of natural products. The presented data indicated that the flavonoids isolated act differently on the bacterial species tested.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the present study showed that the microbiological investigation should be performed, as a routine test, to all infertile men attending to infertility clinics. It should be noticed that presence of urogenital tract infection and inflammation must be eradicated by antibiotic and anti-inflammatory treatment, especially before using Assisted Reproductive Techniques (ART). Flavonoids of the selected plants have a good antioxidant and antibacterial activity, and can be used for medicinal and therapeutic applications.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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